

METHODS OF USING DIDACTIC GAMES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S THINKING

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Abstract. *This article discusses the methods of using didactic games for the development of children's thinking, the help of didactic games to develop the speech of preschool children, to familiarize them with the environment and nature.*

Keywords: *preschool age, thinking, child, didactic games, game, child, preschool education.*

The main goal of the reforms being carried out in our country is to bring up the future successors as smart, intelligent, well-rounded people in all respects. In preschool educational organizations, it is required to organize each lesson by enriching the world of mental thinking of children of the new age. The knowledge acquired in preschool education, the first worldview formed, the acquired skills and qualifications serve as the main criterion for the next period of a person's life.

It is not without reason that the development of scientific understanding and thinking abilities of children of the age of technology, in which the flow of information and the role of technology in human life is rapidly developing, is more important than ever.

Didactic games serve as an important and effective tool in the formation of a child's personality. Because children of all ages, nations and countries consider play to be their main activity. The child seeks to know the world through the game, his speech, thinking, moral qualities, worldview are formed and developed in the game activity. Every educator who correctly understands the scientific-theoretical and practical importance of this, uses didactic games in their classes as the most effective means of forming the child's cognitive abilities. Of course, it should be recognized that the use of didactic games as an educational tool has always created a need for learning, research, and practical testing.

Education and upbringing of children of preschool age has its own characteristics. This feature is expressed by the new organization of education according to their physiological and psychological symptoms, it is built on the basis of games, and education and games are carried out in harmony and mutual regularity.

Play is an integral part of a child's life. The child gets knowledge and information through the game. They get acquainted with the surrounding environment, natural phenomena, landscapes, objects, birds and animals, and the world of plants. A person becomes aware of his activities, work and life. During the game, the child not only gets acquainted with the events of the external environment, but also expresses his attitude towards these events. He learns to distinguish between good and bad, good and bad, pleasant and unpleasant. In the child's activity, his work-reading and learning are so combined with the game that sometimes it is difficult to notice the difference between them.

Didactic games help to develop the speech of preschool children, introduce them to the environment, nature, and also make it easier to introduce the names of things and where they are used. That is why didactic games are organized on different topics and contents.

The peculiarity of the didactic game as a game activity is that the interaction of the educator with children and children with each other is in the form of a game. The teacher is the participant of the game or his organizer and performs any role required by the action of the game. For example, in the "Shop" game, the content of knowledge is that the buyer tells the signs of the things they want to buy, and the children of the seller have to find out what the required thing is according to the signs given by the buyer.

The game serves to practice observation to improve speech fluency. The rules of the game are to be polite to the seller when choosing what the buyer is going to buy, to look it over and compare it to other items, and to pay, and the seller's job is to listen carefully when the buyer is talking. It consists of taking the things that you ask not to be divided and wrapping them in paper.

A didactic game is a practical activity in which children use knowledge during training. In this regard, the importance of the didactic game is that it creates vital conditions for strengthening mental activity to apply the acquired knowledge in different ways. It will reveal the mistakes made by children and what they are struggling with.

The teacher helps children to correct these mistakes and overcome difficulties. Often, didactic games teach children to use their knowledge in new situations, or they require children to demonstrate different forms of mental activity. For example; In the game "Amazing Bag" children are assigned the task of describing a familiar object, for this the child needs to examine the object from head to toe and remember its characteristic features.

During the didactic game, various mental processes are activated and become voluntary. To understand the idea of the game and to follow it, it is necessary to listen and understand the words of the teacher in order to learn the actions and rules of the game. By organizing an individual didactic game, the educator creates conditions for individual relationships, identifies the reasons for lagging behind in mental activity, and increases the level of growth of such children with a lot of practice.

Children's didactic games are held for the following purposes: to develop the skill of playing didactic riddles, to organize team games; Sorting things by color only Sorting them by big and small Sorting adults and cubes in a regular pattern Playing games based on two-quadrant, hexagonal cross-sectional pictures of objects, etc.

Didactic games in the classes aim to solve the following tasks: observation, the ability to check things, compare them with each other, the ability to notice the small differences in their signs, color, shape, size, material, and tell the changes in the location of things. to develop sensory abilities such as finding the names of animals, plants, and vehicles when describing and classifying them, to develop skills, to develop children's general imagination, to group objects according to common signs, and to fill in good things from parts is to develop skills to play with.

"Stringed beads" game

a) Through this game, the child learns to group objects according to their shape. At first, the educator shows how to place the shapes in order, depending on their size. For example,

The child must finish the task independently.

b) During the game, the child groups objects according to their size. The teacher collects circles (triangles) of different sizes (large - small - large) in a row. The child completes the game independently.

"Find the shape" game

During this game, the child learns to concentrate and distribute his attention, voluntarily chooses the forms offered by the teacher. A sheet of paper with different shapes is placed in front of the child, and the task is to delete only the circle from among these shapes (or show the circle with a finger).

"Find such an object" game

In the course of the game, the child learns to compare objects with each other, distinguish their important signs, find a pair of similar objects or choose one of the presented ones. A picture is placed in front of the child and he is given the task of finding two similar objects

The game "Confused paths"

In this game, the teacher teaches the child to go through the confusing (labyrinth) paths and find the only correct path. If the child is given interesting tasks, he will be more interested in the game. For example: "The cat ran towards the mouse!" He will catch it now. Helping the mouse get to its nest."

The existence of a real life situation in didactic games develops the child's thinking and improves the content of the plot and role-playing game. In the game, a child's great movement experience is formed. Didactic games, as an educational game, belong to the group of games that match the age characteristics of children.

The structure of didactic games in this way provides an opportunity to analyze children's activities. That's why all children act with interest during the game. Didactic games affect the child's emotions and create a positive attitude and interest in learning. Children play the game with great pleasure. and they wait impatiently for the start of the game, involuntarily the joyful scene of tomorrow's school day is embodied in their minds.

Adherence to game technology not only fulfills the purpose of the game, but also has a positive effect on children's psyche.

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